

CLEWs Model for India: Coal Retirement vs Forest Cover for Lowering Emissions

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Executive Summary:

This report comprehensively analyses the potential impacts of two major policy interventions in India's energy and environmental sectors: the retirement of ageing coal plants and the systematic increase in forest cover. Using the CLEWs model, this study compares three scenarios: Business As Usual (BAU), Coal Retirement, and Forest Cover Increase from 2020 to 2050. The analysis aims to evaluate the effectiveness of these interventions in mitigating carbon emissions and their implications for land use and water demand in the context of the urgent and pressing climate crisis, underlining the critical need for immediate action.

In conclusion, the findings of this report strongly recommend the phased retirement of coal plants older than 25 years as a more effective strategy for reducing carbon emissions than an equivalent increase in forest cover. This underscores the critical role of transitioning from fossil fuels in India's climate strategy. While the forest cover increase scenario is beneficial, its long-term effectiveness is compromised due to its higher demands on land and water resources. Therefore, the report suggests that prioritizing coal retirement, alongside increased renewable energy penetration, should be central to India's efforts to achieve its climate and sustainability goals.

1. Introduction

India's rapid economic growth and expanding population have increased demands on its energy resources, necessitating a careful balance between development and environmental sustainability. As one of the most significant contributors to global carbon emissions, India's energy sector plays a pivotal role in the worldwide effort to combat climate change, making the strategic evaluation of potential policy interventions and their long-term impacts a matter of global importance.

Increasing the availability of reliable supply at an affordable price is a developmental imperative. As a result, India has set an ambitious target of 500 Gigawatts (GW) of installed renewable energy capacity by 2030. Despite these targets, India's current energy infrastructure and power generation mix in **Figure 1** highlight the diversity of energy sources nationwide. The map on the left illustrates the geographical distribution of various energy generation facilities, including coal, oil and gas, nuclear, hydro, wind, solar, and biopower plants. This distribution indicates. Additionally, non-fossil sources such as hydro, nuclear, wind and solar make up over 40% of the total installation capacity, showcasing the ongoing efforts to diversify energy production and reduce dependence on fossil fuels.

The pie charts on the right provide a snapshot of India's power capacity and generation as of June 2024. The first pie chart shows the total installed capacity of 446 GW, with coal accounting for nearly half of this capacity (48.77%). Solar and wind energy also constitute a significant portion, with 19.16% and 10.46%, respectively, underscoring the country's growing investments in renewable energy (RE). The second pie chart reflects the power generation mix, where coal's dominance is even more pronounced, contributing to 74.34% of total generation. This stark contrast between installed capacity and actual generation highlights India's challenges in scaling renewable energy production to meet its energy demands and environmental goals.

Figure 1: India power map 2024

India's economy is significantly anchored in agriculture despite its declining share in the overall GDP, which is now less than 15%. Approximately 70% of the rural population relies on agriculture for their livelihoods, making it a vital food security and development sector (TERI 2017). The agricultural industry in India is characterized by high water usage, with significant reliance on groundwater and surface water for irrigation. India accounts for about 17% of the world's population but possesses only 4% of global freshwater resources, leading to increasing competition for water among agricultural, industrial, and domestic uses. To address these intertwined challenges of water scarcity and agricultural productivity, the CLEWs approach is essential.

The primary focus of the modelling is to understand the dynamics of the energy-land-food nexus up to the year 2050, particularly in the context of rising demand and evolving policy

targets. By analyzing different scenarios, the model aims to project the changes in carbon emissions resulting from the phased retirement of coal plants, particularly those operational for over 25 years. This could help reduce GHG emissions, improve financial viability, and release capital to support future RE growth.

It also assumes a significant increase in the penetration of renewable energy sources as coal plants retire. This assumption is critical as it reflects the potential for renewables to replace the energy capacity lost from coal, thereby contributing to emission reductions. Additionally, a worst-case scenario is considered, where electricity imports may become necessary if the domestic energy supply falls short due to the accelerated retirement of coal plants. This highlights the importance of strategic planning in energy transition policies, emphasizing the crucial role of policymakers in ensuring that emission reduction targets are met without compromising energy security.

2. Methodology:

In this research, the CLEWs framework was applied using the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) tool. While OSeMOSYS was initially developed for energy systems analysis, its functionality and flexibility permit its adaptation to the integrated analysis of CLEWs. This approach facilitates a comprehensive assessment of the interactions and interdependencies among climate, land, energy, and water systems, enabling a whole systems approach to decision-making. The starter data kit provided for India and the national databases served as the baseline model, incorporating the reference energy system developed, as shown in **Figure 2**. Additionally, agriculture and water data were sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and the International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

Figure 2: Reference CLEWs diagram - India

- With the existing data for 2020 - 2024, projections were made till 2070, assuming the following factors:
 - Annual GDP growth rate - 6.5%,
 - Annual population growth rate – 0.7%
 - Energy demand keeping in mind the national target of 500 GW renewable energy installation by 2030

The results generated for energy demand, land cover type, and water demand serve as a BAU scenario with existing policy targets, as shown in Figures 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 3: Energy demand projection – Scenario 1

Figure 4: Land cover type – Scenario 1

Figure 5: Water demand – Scenario 1

It can be inferred that energy demand will increase sevenfold by 2070. The import electricity technology has been included in the scenario only for the model to run successfully, as the demand exceeded generation by 2053. Similarly, to compensate for the growth in food demand, agricultural land is prioritized over forest land, and it plateaus because a minimum area of $294.61 \cdot 10^3 \text{sq.km}$ is kept as a minimum limit. The water demand will also increase four-fold by 2070. Interestingly, the decrease in water demand around 2037 is due to crops being grown using rainfed instead of irrigation technology. The sudden increase in demand between 2053 and 2062 results from the additional water needed for agriculture made available due to irrigation. Despite the increased share of non-fossil sources, carbon emissions in this scenario peaked at 3700 million tonnes of CO₂eq, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Carbon emissions – Scenario 1

3. Results

Two scenarios were studied to understand water and land use's main impact on lowering carbon emissions. 1) increase in forest area by 0.1% yearly (based on previous average decadal growth) and 2) retiring of coal plants of about 50 GW in a phased manner from 2031 for plants which are over 25 years/ inefficient/ underutilized.

The comparison study was limited to 2020 – 2050 to negate the effects of importing electricity and instead focus on emissions from domestic energy production, which sometimes have a lower/ higher carbon footprint, as per the case. It is also for developing strategies that align with national climate goals and commitments under international agreements. A comparison of annual emissions is plotted for the scenario, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 7: Comparison of CO2 emissions for three CLEWs scenarios

It can be observed that the coal retirement strategy will have the lowest carbon emissions by 2050, and its effects can be seen from the year of implementation. It is almost 0.5 to 1 billion tonnes lower than the other scenarios. While it is understandable that fossil fuel is essential to India's growing needs, delivering access to electricity to the growing population and ensuring energy security, it should also look at the scope and viability of this policy recommendation given the significant decrease in emissions which may align with its NDC or net-zero strategy.

4. Discussion:

The CLEWs approach to integrated systems management emerges as a valuable tool. It offers a holistic analysis that extends beyond climate considerations to encompass the integration of energy, land, and water systems. This whole systems perspective becomes especially pertinent as these systems are inherently interconnected, highlighting the importance of considering their collective impact.

It is also important to acknowledge the limitations of this exercise, which relies on a simplified RES for India. The model, while informative, does not encompass the full spectrum of energy, land, and water systems. For example, agriculture demand projections are based on four crops. Consequently, the insights developed offer a partial view of the implications and potentials of different pathways. Recognising these constraints leads to opportunities for future research that builds upon this foundation, expanding the model to provide a more faithful representation of India's complex energy, land, and water systems.

Potential areas for further research include representing technologies such as pump hydro, modular nuclear reactors, battery storage, green hydrogen, and CCUS and analysing their influence over the country's energy options. More accurate data on the agricultural and water sector, the scope of using recycled water in agriculture and industrial demand, etc. Expanding the scope to transportation transitions, among others, will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play.

5. Conclusion:

The findings suggest that retiring coal plants is a more effective strategy for reducing carbon emissions than increasing forest cover, with a difference of nearly half a billion tonnes. While both interventions contribute to emissions reduction, coal retirement has the added benefits of reducing water demand and freeing up land for alternative uses. This report underscores the importance of prioritizing coal retirement in India's energy policy to meet emission reduction targets and promote sustainable development.

Future work should focus on refining the model with more detailed datasets, anticipating growth in energy demand, and exploring the socio-economic impacts of these interventions to provide a more comprehensive understanding of their long-term viability. It is crucial to prioritize the potential impact on the workforce to reduce the transition costs, free up capital for future renewable energy investment, and alleviate financial strain on the power sector.

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